
THE DEVELOPMENT OF A MUSICAL THEATER ACTOR'S VOICE
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В этой статье рассматривается важность голоса актера музыкального театра.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance of a musical theater actor's voice.

Ключевые слова: Актерское мастерство, действие слова, характер, образ, жест, режиссер, спектакль.

Keywords: Acting, word action, character, image, gesture, director, performance.

Action is divided into two types: activity — that is, the subject's spontaneous (independent, free) influence on objective reality — and reaction, that is, activity arising from the influence of objective reality upon the subject. Objective reality, as we can see, must be present in both cases; without it, no activity is possible. However, its mere objective existence is insufficient — the subject must experience it in some way. This lived experience of objective reality is referred to as verbal action. Thus, verbal action in the process of reading a literary text and revealing its stylistic nature constitutes the essence and significance of the actor's continuous professional life or “experience” in creating a stage image. Verbal action is a deep and multifaceted psychological process that depends on the individual characteristics of each artist, especially the actor. It is no coincidence that the fundamental views of the great theorist of acting Konstantin Stanislavski and the distinguished Kazakh theatre scholar Mukhtar Baiserke-nev coincide regarding verbal action in the process of reading a text; each sought to profoundly explain its importance in the creation of a stage image. Verbal action in reading a literary text represents a holistic reflection of objective reality that arises from the direct impact of real-world objects upon the human senses. It includes perceiving the object as a whole, differentiating its individual features, selecting informational content relevant to the purpose of action, and forming a sensory image. Verbal action is connected with thinking, memory, and attention, and it becomes integrated into practical activity and communication processes. At the end of the nineteenth century, theatre was closely associated with its own repertoire and with sketch-like plays depicting ready-made facts lying on the surface of life. The lack of thematic depth and authenticity was concealed behind external plausibility and carefully accumulated everyday details. Plays of this period confined actors within superficial life characteristics, encouraging external typification and imitation of speech that emphasized formal traits of character, worldview, or

nationality. The “truth” of such theatre was theatricalized; its realism and stage expressiveness were distinguished by conventional speech and memorized vocal modulation. Traditional methods of expressing emotion, along with codified gestures and tonal patterns, were transmitted from generation to generation. Great artists, through the force of their talent, broke free from outdated clichés and demonstrated models of passion, vitality, experience, and naturalness. They revealed the living breath of truth and power that served the realization and disclosure of real life. However, in the speech practices of Russian theatre — even during the formation and flourishing of realist art marked by the names of Mikhail Shchepkin, Alexander Ostrovsky, Pavel Mochalov, Maria Yermolova, Mikhail Sadovsky, and Alexander Lensky — by the end of the nineteenth century clearly defined formal clichés had nevertheless emerged. This indicated the lag of art behind the demands and needs of living reality. The intonational techniques of stage speech increasingly entered into deep contradiction with the evolving artistic tasks facing twentieth-century theatre, which sought to respond to the demands of its time and to rethink its expressive means accordingly. As Anatoly Lobanov rightly observed: “There was truth in the Maly Theatre. Let us say Gogol appeared and spoke his truth — and suddenly it became unbearable to listen to people on stage speaking in the pre-Gogolian manner. The Art Theatre arrived and proposed a different rhythm and manner of speaking in life, and beside it the speech style of the Maly Theatre began to seem, so to speak, an anachronism.” Declamation, pathos, and theatrical “stamps,” along with everyday conventional markers, became obstacles to the development of theatrical art. A refined theatrical consciousness once again intensified its demand for truth in stage speech — truth corresponding to contemporary life, to its needs, anxieties, and emotional experiences, and to the authenticity of life on stage. At the end of the nineteenth century, the Music and Drama School of the Philharmonic Society played

a special role in shaping new approaches to actor training. Within its walls, in 1891, at the special invitation of Alexander Yuzhin, Vladimir Nemirovich-Danchenko began teaching dramatic art to actors. Nemirovich-Danchenko worked at the school with great enthusiasm and dedication for more than a decade, until 1901. During this time, he trained several generations of actors, including such major theatre figures as Olga Knipper, Ivan Moskvina, Vsevolod Meyerhold, Nina Litovtseva, Maria Savitskaya, and Sofia Khalyutina. His pedagogical activity at the Philharmonic School possessed immense and transformative significance for the Russian theatre school. During these years, his creative method took shape, as well as his approach to resolving the fundamental artistic and methodological issues involved in training an actor of high culture, genuine stage truth, and elevated civic consciousness. Nemirovich-Danchenko regarded theatrical pedagogy as an entirely new approach to actor training and as a means of creating a new theatre. As a playwright, writer, director, and public figure, he formulated the tasks of “initiating into art” as follows: “To preserve individuality, to bring a ‘spark’ into life, to assist its development, to work constantly with human material, to saturate it with one’s best ideas — this is the seed of theatre, its deepest and most captivating essence...” Before Nemirovich-Danchenko’s arrival at the Philharmonic School, instruction in theatrical creativity was far from satisfactory. He later recalled: “The educational significance of the theatre school was completely disregarded; it was impossible to convince anyone of the importance of voice production, diction, flexibility, dance, fencing, and general educational courses.” The traditions of great actors had been forgotten, and no systematic training existed. Pedagogy was limited to preparing roles and developing techniques for expressing emotions. The pedagogical position closest to Nemirovich-Danchenko’s principles and demands was that of Alexander Lensky, who worked with rare dedication at the Maly Theatre School. Nemirovich-Danchenko and Lensky, discussing both general and specific issues of theatrical pedagogy in detail, sought to share their explorations, experiments, and achievements with one another. With exceptional persistence, Nemirovich-Danchenko searched for methods and means to combat the inertia of theatrical art and pedagogy, as well as routine formulas and clichés. He criticized the theatre school for deriving not from life, but from stage stereotypes — for teaching the depiction of external aspects of life, the repetition of emotional schemes, and the memorization of theatrical clichés. Therefore, he insisted with particular force on the radical restructuring of the system of theatrical education. Nemirovich-Danchenko rejected the old practice of preparing roles; he denied technology for technology’s sake, and reading for reading’s sake. He sought ways to educate an artist capable of living on stage, of revealing the character of an image, of sensing truth, and of thinking and creating independently. As he wrote: “Above all, I seek authenticity and a serious artistic foundation. The professor’s task is to teach students to think about the characters they portray and to show them how a role should be per-

ceived.” Even at that time, Vladimir Nemirovich-Danchenko believed that in order to free the actor’s art from falsehood and cliché, simple and truthful speech was essential. A considerable part of his pedagogical work was therefore devoted to cultivating the actor’s speech — its expressiveness, brightness, and simplicity, as well as its clarity and richness. This can be observed in the detailed substantiations of his teaching program, in his requirements concerning “tone” and diction, and in his notes on individual students, where he consistently evaluated their data and achievements from the standpoint of stage speech: “Knipper: noble diction, honest tone, very intelligent declamation. Savitskaya: tone clear in the sense of sincerity and beauty, not entirely precise, yet free from vulgarity and coarseness.” In his work on tone, Nemirovich-Danchenko paid particular attention to such concepts as artistic taste, vitality, simplicity, lightness, richness of imagination, verbal action, the раскрытие stylistic nature of the text, correct understanding of the role, and perceptiveness. In his work on diction, he emphasized the voice, the beauty and strength of sound, the ability to command it, purity and clarity of articulation, authenticity, and variety of intonation. In working with the word, he demanded not merely technical excellence in pronunciation, but above all the naturalness and vitality of speech, the accurate transmission of thoughts, feelings, and moods grounded in comprehensive analysis of the material and deep psychological interpretation of its content, as well as the revelation of the stylistic nature of the text. We find confirmation of this in his directorial practice, for example in his production plan for Julius Caesar (referring to the staging of Shakespeare’s tragedy). Nemirovich-Danchenko focused closely on the logical structure of the text. He carefully analyzed the semantic and intonational character of each phrase in Brutus’s monologue, relating it to the character’s personality, actions, objectives, and thoughts. By answering questions such as, “Why does the character speak in this way at this very moment, and not differently?”, he took decisive steps toward understanding verbal action through uncovering the stylistic nature of the text. Not only professional training, but also the comprehensive cultivation of the actor’s personality constituted the essence of his pedagogy. This marked a new stage and a significant advance in theatrical education. In the struggle for a new theatre that reflected life — for social and artistic truth, and for a new type of actor — the struggle for the living, active word occupied a special place. “The old template had to be broken... In order to free ourselves from the conventional mastery of transmitting stage experience... it was necessary to shake off the entire shell of conventions in intonation and vocal modulation, to achieve the highest simplicity of theatrical speech, yet without rendering it dull, pale, or colorless, and without depriving it of lyrical shading. The simplicity of verbal action does not mean excessively simplified speech as in everyday life.” Understanding stage speech as a mode of being and communication became one of the most important aspects of the new theatre’s aesthetics. Naturally, this development was made possible by new dramaturgy. Above all, one may mention the plays of Anton Chekhov, although his works were not staged at

either the Alexandrinsky Theatre or the Maly Theatre at first. The renewal of dramaturgy, striving to reveal the depth and substance of life, was directly connected with progressive literature. The dramatic novel of Fyodor Dostoevsky, the dramaturgy of Leo Tolstoy, and the plays of Chekhov — all sought to portray the human being in the full complexity of spiritual life. They revealed not only objective connections expressed in textual structure, but also deeper additional meanings and the stylistic nature of the text. From the understanding of subtext arose verbal action. From their very first attempts to create a new theatre, Konstantin Stanislavski and Nemirovich-Danchenko showed a deliberate and profound interest in theatrical speech traditions. Stanislavski singled out Pavel Mochalov from the entire theatrical world rich in talent as a genius who addressed epoch-making problems. His aspiration toward genuine experience, the unexpectedness and spontaneity of verbal action, the naturalness of speech, his capacity to reveal inner life and the stylistic nature of the text — more than the declamatory manner of the old romantic school or the deliberately exaggerated everyday speech obscured by an impenetrable shell — deeply convinced audiences and attracted the emerging new theatre. The formation of the artistic method of the Moscow Art Theatre was characterized by reflection on the living word, by the search for ways to achieve the highest simplicity of speech, and by a complete rejection of traditionally canonized stage verbal action. In the search for the “truth of feeling in given circumstances,” the theatre sought a new, contemporary manner of speech. However, the revolution in stage speech was not only about rejecting everyday similarities, old speech canons, or the usual conventions; it was also about the very idea of creating truth in stage interactions instead of using literal words. Behind the text lay the world of thoughts, viewpoints, and emotions that underlie human behavior and give rise to words in life, as well as its stylistic nature. The emphasis on inner action and inner life, rather than the external, revealed the causes and connections of thoughts and words, generated their flow, and brought to light the inner forces that determine the life of speech, reflecting a desire to uncover the text’s stylistic nature. This idea was manifested in the 1898 production of *The Seagull*. Everything in the play served to reveal this inner life: the free *mise-en-scène* that obeyed no tradition, the flow of life continuing behind the stage, the sound of rain, immersing the characters in their everyday worries, distant emotions, and sudden pauses. The manner of speech in the performance was new because theatrical, conventional, elevated speech disappeared. The liveliness and authenticity of speech arose not from external signs of reality, but from the truthfulness of behavior, understanding the thoughts, and grasping the stylistic nature of the text. The laws of reading a stage text had long been known, but they did not apply in the new theatrical processes. This does not mean that simple and vital speech laws did not exist. On the contrary, “the ability to speak simply and beautifully is a science with its own rules.” But the theater did not know these rules. They had to be carefully studied and mastered. The entire creative practice of the founders of artistic

theater was connected with discovering the true organic laws of living speech on stage. Theater specialists understood that one should not “act” any emotion, mood, stance, word, style, or image; instead, the stylistic nature of the text had to be revealed and realized through the effectiveness of speech. Behind the protest against artificial speech was always respect for the author’s word and the desire to convey it to the audience accurately and convincingly. Yet while valuing the word, just as an artist judges its color and tone, or a musician evaluates sound, the founders of the new theater considered it an unchangeable truth: the actor’s word had to exist on the same level as all elements of the creative process, arising naturally, organically, as a direct result of inner life. The theater persistently sought methods to work with speech that would correspond to the entire actor’s system. Adapting speech for direct stage expression was a completely different process. The idea of returning to *The Seagull* arose to draw the actor’s attention to particular details: “a match and a burning cigarette in the dark, powder in Arkadina’s pocket, Sorin’s blanket, a comb, a cuff, washing hands, drinking water, and so on... The actor had to be trained to perform these actions so that speech would become easier.” Sometimes the striving to make speech lifelike and natural stemmed from a heightened interest in speech characteristics, where speech became a means for the theater to create the truthfulness of the character’s behavior. This led to ethnographic precision in paying attention to speech features and details in texts such as L. Tolstoy’s *The Power of Darkness* and M. Gorky’s *The Lower Depths*, and in capturing the stylistic nature of the text. Yet for theater directors, the most crucial adaptation for living speech appeared to be the actor’s organic life activity. K. S. Stanislavski, reflecting on the production of L. Andreyev’s *The Life Drama*, wrote in the chapter “Revealing Familiar Truths” that he had kept actors away from rigid *mise-en-scène* decisions. Stanislavski feared that *mise-en-scène* could distort the inner process, conceal it, push it into the background, or even replace living behavior with “muscle memory.” Therefore, he “eliminated the *mise-en-scène*.” In 1909, Stanislavski staged I. Turgenev’s *A Month in the Country* using a strictly static approach. M. V. Dobuzhinsky’s remarkable set design, with its enclosed depth, symmetrical stage images, and carefully indicated transitional passages, was cut away. All the director’s attention was focused on the inner process. His detailed commentary revealed what lay behind each line, what performers should feel and understand. At that time, the principle he called “illumination” was extremely important: a sequence of actor tasks, based on careful analysis, ensured physical comfort and revealed the subtext of speech. In Stanislavski’s directorial notes, there is clear and general guidance showing that the content and stylistic nature of the text is revealed through subtext, which produces the effectiveness of speech. In the second act of this play, the text reads: Natalya Petrovna: “No, please, do not shoot toward the garden. Save this poor bird... Moreover, you will startle your grandmother.” K. S. Stanislavski (p. 19) noted: “These words should not be understood literally; the point is that there seems to be an additional meaning or

subtext in them, like ‘I love you,’ ‘I want to be with you.’” His directorial notes also contain purely technical instructions: “speaks loudly” (p. 24), “the speech manner and tone of the teacher, that is, a lady of the style of that time” (p. 30), “silent, as if hiding from others” (p. 35), “speaks very simply and quietly” (p. 35), “I am in love, simply, slowly, as if reading the letters of this feeling” (p. 36), “at a fast pace” (p. 37). These instructions are few, and all are aimed at revealing subtext, the stylistic nature of the text, how to convey it to the audience, how to express the effectiveness of speech, to enhance and refine physical well-being, and to adapt performance organically. Vladimir Ivanovich Nemirovich-Danchenko and K. S. Stanislavski understood that seeking the life truth of a word, uncovering the stylistic nature of a text, and achieving it were not easy tasks. Even though Stanislavski disliked the study process when working on A. P. Chekhov’s plays, he engaged extensively with hexameter. The actor’s vocal capabilities—their beauty, clarity, and sound potential—were important for Nemirovich-Danchenko in addressing purely creative challenges. At the Moscow Art Theatre’s stage, in the premiere of *Three Sisters*, the role of Olga was performed by the highly captivating actress M. G. Savitskaya. Savitskaya, with her uniquely beautiful voice that had once started with *Antigone*, played the elderly daughter with heartfelt delicacy. Her beautiful voice allowed Nemirovich-Danchenko to perceive the poetic nuance needed to convey Chekhov’s language and the stylistic simplicity inherent in the author’s text. After Savitskaya passed away, the actress O. Butova aspired to play Olga. Despite recognizing Butova’s abilities and talent, Nemirovich-Danchenko did not deem it appropriate to assign her this role. In a letter to Shechepkina, Butova admitted: “Nemirovich-Danchenko spoke wonderfully. He said everything that could be said to an actress, but overall, portraying Olga is not my task; he said my talent is limited... My voice is my greatest obstacle.” From production to production, from role to role, Nemirovich-Danchenko’s advice, his notes on speech manner and nature, and guidance on “finding the character’s speech” accumulated. In a letter to M. S. Stanislavski (1902), discussing the role of Satin in M. Gorky’s *The Lower Depths*, Nemirovich-Danchenko emphasized the need to develop a new technique: “Develop rapid, effortless speech without pauses. Words must flow from your mouth easily and continuously.” After the Great October Socialist Revolution, an integrated approach emerged in the creative practice of the Moscow Art Theatre: speech was considered the most important component of a performance; stage speech became an internally managed process dependent on the speaker’s objectives, circumstances, relationships, individual characteristics, and psychophysical condition. M. O. Knebel recalled: “To create a living character, generate the effectiveness of speech, and reveal the stylistic nature of the text, actors needed versatile, varied, and expressive speech. This was an essential condition for working on the production.” The living soul of a phrase is sensed internally but expressed with taste. Work on subtext and acting technique are closely interconnected. Choosing breath, lightness, subtlety, rhythm, and the expressiveness of

sound requires developing vocal technique and mastery, while simultaneously uncovering the effectiveness of speech and the stylistic nature of the text in the creative process and reading. By the late 1930s, Nemirovich-Danchenko’s key methodological principle was clearly articulated: “A word arises from the seed of the actor’s psychophysical character in the role.” He explained this inner connection as follows: “An actor achieves the right path in creating a stage image by understanding the thinking, character, and stylistic nature of the text of the character he or she embodies. From this, movement qualities and speech manner, as well as the effectiveness of speech, naturally arise.” While working on *Three Sisters*, Nemirovich-Danchenko consistently returned to the idea of emotional ignition and the actor’s physical well-being. To give birth to a word, one must “plant the emotional seed,” and for this, all behavior, thoughts, and feelings must adapt to the stage situation, giving rise to the effectiveness of speech. “This was the most important aspect for me during preparation,” he said. An actor’s mood develops from understanding the typical traits, complexities, and contradictions of the characters in the play, their relationships with people, their individual characteristics, life experiences, profession, biography, and the unity of their personal qualities. Nemirovich-Danchenko moved from the character, lifestyle, thought, temperament, and physical and behavioral state to the actor’s speech. “Begin to imagine what he is like. Perhaps your speed of speech is too fast for Chebutykin? He is slow, filled with life experience, and therefore cannot speak quickly” (Gribov – Chebutykin).

“When Olga walks around the room, she communicates all of this” (p. 51, 181) (Elanskaya – Olga). He further instructed Elanskaya: “Olga is the eldest in the house; she is not sentimental, but impressive; she is the future head of the gymnasium; she speaks clearly... One must endure such simplicity to speak more precisely...” To Georgievskaya – Natasha: “...because there is coldness in her inner world... therefore she speaks firmly, harshly, and with authority.” We will not continue with examples, but we note the ideas of Nemirovich-Danchenko and Stanislavski: their thoughts deeply connect all aspects of speech with a person’s individuality, personal and emotional traits, and are among the most important and forward-looking from the perspective of understanding the laws of modern speech communication. The development of speech art in the Soviet theater was based on strengthening the realist traditions of the actor’s school and on cultivating civic consciousness and the social significance of theater. Before the Great Patriotic War, Soviet theater was distinguished by highly professional mastery of stage speech. Its traditions were shaped under the influence of the classical Russian school of speech, while creative approaches were renewed through Soviet theater practice. The culture of theatrical speech was enriched with sounds, rhythms, shades of socialist reality, intonations, expressiveness, and the style of Soviet dramaturgy. An important factor in the formation of the Soviet school of speech was the creative influence of the leading Soviet directorial trend: for example, the work of A. I. Dikiy, A. D. Popov, N. P. Okhlopov, A. M. Lobanov,

and Yu. A. Zavadsky. Alongside K. S. Stanislavski, who considered the enactment of the word on stage—that is, speech effectiveness and revealing the stylistic nature of the text—as a crucial element, Vladimir Ivanovich Nemirovich-Danchenko’s influence was also significant. For actors in the 1920s–1940s, speech and voice were the primary focus. Actors such as B. V. Shchukin, M. F. Astangov, M. I. Babanov, and N. M. Mordvinov stood out for their exceptional voices, intelligent, free, and expressive speech, nuanced articulation, and musicality. Beyond this, behind each word there lay a real, bold, and confident contemporary feeling, deeply and passionately engaged with the purpose at hand. The brightness and fullness of the voice, the expressiveness of diction, the clarity and scale of speech, its carefully considered and confident expressiveness, unique personal intonation, dynamic range, and tempo-rhythm—all these were distinctive features of Moscow Art Theatre actors’ manner of speech. The actors’ speech created a special atmosphere imbued with the breath of stage reality. Yet this was not only the actor’s truth; it was also a purified, stylized, and heightened truth born from adherence to the author’s manner, an expressive and image-based reality. During the Soviet period, Nemirovich-Danchenko’s directorial work crystallized the principles of creating living speech on stage. Plays, requiring a synthesis of life, social, and theatrical truths, demanded the director’s most engaged and exacting work with the word. The specificity and truth of stage speech for Nemirovich-Danchenko lay first and foremost in precisely understanding and clarifying the author’s style. How the author’s idea should be expressed, and by what expressive means it could be conveyed, was equally important: “...you only use the author’s idea, subordinating their vocabulary to everyday speech. The author’s individual intonation always lives in a good play... If we do not hear it, we cease to have the ‘author’s theater.’ Then we limit ourselves to content alone, neglecting expressive complexity. Then it no longer matters how it is written, and creativity, art, stops. This leads to a general decline in the theater. Only a ‘general simplicity’ remains.” Everyday, life-like speech, in the works of A. Ostrovsky, M. Gorky, A. Chekhov, L. Leonov, and N. Pogodin, was sublimated behind the text, in the author’s style and in the actor’s speech, through the expressive plasticity of words, tonal relief, boldness and clarity of intonation, and rhythmic articulation. Actors complemented and revealed the speech traits of the environment provided by the author, carefully and lovingly using pronunciation, dialect, emphasis, and individual speech characteristics. Naturalness was combined with remarkable expressiveness, musicality, purity, fullness, and variety. Their speech reflected the requirements of the time: its aesthetics, rhythm, and orthoepic and phonetic culture. The best Soviet actors of the 1920s–1940s were exceptional in both individuality and manner of expression, collectively representing the speech art of their era. K. S. Stanislavski and Nemirovich-Danchenko, defining ways to create life on stage, developed an approach to living stage speech based on the effectiveness of words, grounded in the precise alignment of actions, imagination, and stage tasks, and in absolutely

exact communicative means. Stanislavski’s system began forming before the revolution (at least from 1907), rooted in early theatrical experiments. Yet it was during the Soviet era, when its guiding principles were articulated and by the 1930s, that the Stanislavski system solidified as a creative method of Soviet theater. Like any living phenomenon, it developed and evolved through the theater’s life experience and specific creative conditions. If the foundation of this system is a super-task, the theory of action, and stable values, if the ways to create “the life of the human spirit” and the actor’s lived experience serve as an objective method of creativity, then expressiveness, external technique, and representational methods are naturally flexible and changeable. The measure of truth, realism of stage speech, and the culture of speech are determined by contemporary reality, its requirements, norms, and aesthetic and ideological standards. The fundamental rupture in the tradition of stage speech before the war was marked by the Great Patriotic War, which transformed the entire life of theater and decisively affected stage speech. Humanity went through suffering and heroic trials; the meaning of tragedy was revealed sharply and harshly, and spiritual values were expressed with unprecedented intensity and power. Understanding humanity’s place in the postwar world required civic maturity and natural authenticity in depicting life, abandoning embellishment of human relationships. Traditional forms of external acting technique hindered performance: imitation, prepared intonation, memorized pauses and emphases were increasingly felt, becoming standardized for decades, and thereby often disrupting the living processes of truth. The general accepted tradition of theatrical speech declined in representing the essence of life phenomena in the best postwar Soviet plays. Artists seeking a new aesthetic ideal found in theater, behind simple exterior speech, the concrete, everyday matters that revealed the inner life of characters. Of course, this was speech that served “only itself”; understanding its content and the inner life of existence on stage could occur only under high creative conditions, when directors and actors could reveal deep, living processes. At that time, in *Sovremennik* theater productions, real life was conveyed on stage clearly and sincerely. The everyday similarity of intonation in G. A. Tovstonogov’s bold directorial decisions created high tension in events, while the truth of feelings and thoughts in A. V. Efros’s productions was lived and performed authentically by remarkable actors. The experience of young *Sovremennik* actors, born within the walls of the Moscow Art Theatre and its school, embodied the realism of the Moscow Art Theatre, the immediacy and authenticity of contemporary relationships, and a thirst to speak in a living, modern language reflecting the realities of the time. In creating a new theater, O. N. Efremov had to address the full range of civic, human, and artistic concerns. Solving these issues required a new drama that could depict the people’s new life experience, in which young actors could portray the destinies and lives of their contemporaries and peers deeply and fully. Perhaps for this reason, V. Rozov’s *Forever Alive* became one of the theater’s most compelling, daring, and authentic productions. Themes of war, life, love, loyalty, and

selflessness were presented in a way that was heartfelt, relevant, and innovative. Young actors approached each performance as a personal struggle. They lived through their characters' lives and were infinitely truthful. The vivid structure and stylistics of Rozov's highly cultured play found expression in the everyday reality of life and in the authenticity of the actors' speech. Stage speech held a unique place in the aesthetics of the new theater. By setting clear artistic goals, Efremov taught actors the skill of conveying the final objective through the unfolding of each role. Emerging from living, active stage behavior, actors explored how each character would conduct themselves relative to the pressing purpose of the performance. The question "Why?" was never abandoned throughout the role work. Secondary but fully realized truths—the emotional precision of inner life, the absolute reliability of movement and gesture—all began with, and gained momentum from, the word. Speech on stage was neutral in phonetic and stylistic qualities. This was reinforced by the author's everyday vocabulary and the credible ordinariness of the play's characters. The actors of the Moscow Art Theatre were trained in drama, and its style and imagery significantly shaped the theater's manner of speech. Questions of speech distinctiveness and speech characterization revealed the personal traits of character and role, playing a major role in their work. For the actors in Efremov's theater, most of whom were portraying their contemporaries, the role was above all the "I" of a person placed in an unfamiliar situation. Efremov developed actors' abilities through large, cohesive episodes, moving through entire segments of a role toward the central objective. In semantically concentrated episodes, speech could carry weight and significance, with the word taking precedence. In Rozov's *Forever Alive*, the theater's manner of speech appeared credible and vivid. For example, Veronica (A. B. Pokrovskaya) runs into the room hopelessly and flustered, grabbing tables, chairs, and cabinets, as if seeking a support to rescue. From the torrent of grief carrying Veronica, only the essential words emerge, held as if by someone drowning in water. In the speech of the best actors of the 1950s–1960s, words were delivered in a new, living manner, growing from a deep interplay of elements. However, the power that came from the truth—its resemblance to reality, intellectual assimilation, and precision of action—could, if reduced to mechanical replication, immediately turn against itself. This is a natural occurrence. Everyday speech, as in life, conveys no meaningful process, yet in imitation it easily takes root and creates the illusion of truth. The desire to remove layers of resemblance and habit sought to cleanse stage speech and acting skills from clichés, to search for new, even deeper ways to depict life on stage. Yet in seeking living speech, while avoiding theatrically stylized pronunciation, only the superficial features of everyday speech developed: displayed words, quiet speech, "under-delivered," calm, monotonous, "non-actor" voices, slow articulation, incompleteness, and gaps in sound. A whole recent period of theater practice became closely associated with "whispering realism," self-serving expression, and mannerless, dim, indistinct, theatricalized

sentences. Many qualities of theatrical speech came to be labeled as mere theatricality. Well-prepared voices, polished speech, carefully measured sentences based on grammatical logic, exact pauses, speech accents, rising and falling intonation—all hid uncertain, artificial, lifeless content. If declamation was the hallmark against which early 20th-century fine theater fought, by mid-century the hallmark had become quiet, gray, and muted speech. This conventionalized, external, imitative method, canonized as part of acting technique, led to a crisis in the art of stage speech and affected the most important and profound inner qualities of acting. This phenomenon, often considered speech neutrality, reflected a significant decline in the theater's speech culture. "There are now two extreme situations regarding the word," wrote G. A. Tovstonogov. "On one hand, the pursuit of a modern approach to being on stage, realism, and fighting declamation has led to neglecting theatrical speech through deliberate word play. This undermines the nature of our art... There is another old problem. This is the actor turning the word into a self-sufficient element, after which the effective process stops, and speech begins in isolation. In this case, the nature of theater is also disrupted." In searching for a new, living, and more organic way for the actor to inhabit a role—regardless of approach—if it is aimed at deepening our ideas about life truth on stage, the word is placed in the foreground. In other words, all the subtlety of experience is represented and rendered visible. If the rejection of the word is merely an attempt to mimic contemporary life, the very meaning of theater disappears. Unfortunately, the formal methodology of creating everyday-like word effectiveness, speech, and whispering became commonplace. Directors' primitiveness, the inability to translate the super-task into action, and the neglect of the expressive potential of the author's language often led to imitation of the worst examples of poor, quotidian speech, rather than portraying vitality authentically and integrating it with speech and stage realism. Striving to speak words well, loudly, and clearly is not effective if it does not conceal the genuinely internalized, purposeful, and living relationships. Soft murmuring and emphatic scolding are two sides of the same coin. Stage speech today demands deeper and more subtle methods to reveal the actor's inner life and delicate inner technique, imposing special requirements on direction. The effectiveness of speech on stage, contemporary speech, and its distinctiveness can be assessed in direct connection with truth and with the theatrical processes of the last decade. Attention to "today's" vibrant speech on stage depends on several factors, the most important being the characteristics of contemporary art, its principles, and the refinement of our ideas about its measures. Radio, cinema, television—any mass medium brings the actor closer to the audience. Modern technologies have entered theater life directly, but without exerting overwhelming influence. Sound and image are very close to the viewer; the actor's art becomes part of everyday life, of everyday reality. Norms for perceiving living speech, its height or ordinary scale, theatricality or simplicity—all underwent profound change. A wide audience, varying in education and cultural background, remained in constant

contact with the actor's art. Under this influence, the audience's artistic taste and aesthetic perception developed, as did their understanding of the "resemblance" of human behavior in real life and the actor's behavior on screen and stage (either heightened or dimmed). Another crucial factor was the ability to perceive stage reality and the effectiveness of speech. The skill of recognizing realistic behavior and hearing living speech was honed. Despite changes in perception and the proximity of daily life in theater, the criteria for live interaction on stage, as opposed to television or cinema screens, remained uncompromised. The effectiveness of stage speech in contemporary theater is influenced not only by the director's concept for a production but also by the development and transformation of the actor's art itself. The demand for natural, conversational language in today's theater is not merely legitimate—it is essential. The key question is how to understand and achieve this conversational speech. K. S. Stanislavski and V. I. Nemirovich-Danchenko considered the simplicity and naturalness of spoken language an inseparable and even defining element of theatrical art. Although Stanislavski noted, "Most people speak poorly and crudely in everyday life..." life itself served as a standard for him in measuring stage speech and verbal action. He asked, "Have you ever heard extremely simple speech on stage or in life—without extraordinary vocal effort, without rising or falling dramatically, without excessive stretching of sound intervals, without complex phonetic figures or intonational patterns? Despite the absence of all these methods to intensify expressiveness, very simple speech often produces an incomparable effect through its logic, coherence, clear grouping of words, structural organization of phrases, endurance of delivery, clarity of thought, and precision of lexical expression." Stanislavski's reflections and research in speech and voice were aimed at finding the optimal ways to cultivate stage speech as true, living, and organic speech. The central principle of such speech was, naturally, verbal action. "In life, people always speak with some goal, task, or necessity, always aiming to accomplish something through their words." On stage, verbal action arises from actively perceiving and engaging with the stylistic nature of the work, thinking and feeling, and understanding the author's text in a particular way. It is realized through the author's words, as the performer engages with the literary, stylistically refined language of the writer. This language exists as the character's speech—specific, individual, and unique verbal action within the role. Simultaneously, lexical choice, stylistic form, punctuation, and all other expressive tools are closely interconnected, conveying the vividness, emotional content, and stylistic character of the role material. Only in this structure do the typical qualities of the author's speech fully emerge. Theater, in turn, transforms the written speech of the play into living, oral expression and verbal action. It is important to note that while literary written language has been studied extensively for a long time, systematic research into verbal action began only at the end of the 1950s. In recent years, dedicated studies on verbal action have highlighted its distinctive qualities, comparing it not only with written language

but also with other forms of spoken speech. Verbal action is one of the oral speech styles with its own functions and properties. Its defining features are the "specific environment of the speakers," and its content is determined by the "interests of communication at the given moment." Conversational speech is primarily dialogical, unrehearsed, and always directly dependent on the interlocutor's reception. In verbal action, intonation serves as a form of being—it plays a primary, leading role. To understand the action, task, evaluation, and relationship—in other words, the meaning—intonation is critical. Stress, pauses, and other nonverbal communication tools such as gestures and facial expressions sometimes replace detailed verbal information, allowing ambiguity, continuity, or incompleteness in speech. Researchers of verbal action have noted and identified its unique properties, distinguishing it from the intonation of other functional spoken styles. Its key characteristics—pace, intensity, pauses, and tension—vary infinitely and resist formalization or schematic patterns. Variations depend on the speaker's objectives, the communicative situation, and personal traits. Rapid, slow, relaxed, or unhurried speech occurs side by side, with careful, nearly syllabic articulation and sometimes indistinct endings or omissions of individual sounds. The spontaneity of live, direct speech produces natural pauses and silences. In concrete situations of verbal action, sentences often form continuous wholes, skipping necessary syntactic pauses and featuring non-syntactic, psychological, or physiological breaks. The main features of intonation in oral speech can be summarized as follows:

1. Intonation exhibits significant contrasts—from minimal, almost "colorless" everyday cues in meaning, clarity, and expressiveness, to highly stylized, maximally loud, and clearly expressive intonation in formal speech.

2. The precision of intonation varies, using very high and low tones, abrupt drops, and rises. Oral sentences are marked by alternation of stressed and unstressed elements, which defines both speech production and perception. Smooth alternation of rising and falling tones creates rhythm and eliminates monotony typical of codified literary language.

3. Verbal action is highly emotional ("affective speech is the best way to convey your thought to the interlocutor"). Sustained vowels are a characteristic method.

E. L. Nosenko highlights the role of the "vocal channel"—voice and breathing—in conveying emotional information. Key aspects include:

1. Pronounced deviations in fundamental frequency and intensity of speech signals.

2. Sudden changes in overall speech tone, with increased pace through articulation of speech units.

3. Increased speed of articulation (absolute speech speed).

4. Variation in the duration of the actor's or reader's reaction to cues.

5. Articulatory errors (blurred pronunciation), sometimes transforming speech into singing.

6. Increased number of words distinguished by logical stress.

7. Greater frequency of grammatically and logically incomplete phrases compared with normal speech.

Theater researchers emphasize that incomplete and indistinct articulation in verbal action can hinder comprehension of stage imagery. This ambiguity arises from quantitative and qualitative reductions in vowel sounds, shortening of vowels, loss of consonants, and loss of word beginnings, endings, or connections. All these phenomena are associated with very low intensity and slow articulation. Reduced clarity and imprecision in diction are thus natural features of living speech. Negligence in verbal action in everyday life is compensated by factors such as:

- The speed of interaction with partners
- Nonverbal means of communication
- Opportunities for repetition and correction
- Conversational habits with the interlocutor
- Lack of need for exhaustive phonetic clarity and articulation details for the purposes of dialogue

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